

NANOLETTERS

Title: Single-step process to prepare CeO₂ nanotubes with improved catalytic activity

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ABSTRACT

CeO₂ nanotubes have been grown electrochemically using a porous alumina membrane as a template. The resulting material has been characterized by means of scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray energy dispersive spectroscopy, high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy tomography, high-resolution electron microscopy (HREM), and electron energy loss spectroscopy. According to SEM, the outer diameter of the nanotubes corresponds to the pore size (200 nm) of the alumina membrane, and their length ranges between 30 and 40 μm . HREM images have revealed that the width of the nanotube walls is about 6 nm. The catalytic activity of these novel materials for the CO oxidation reaction is compared to that of a polycrystalline powder CeO₂ sample prepared by a conventional route. The activity of the CeO₂ nanotubes is shown to be in the order of 400 times higher per gram of oxide at 200 °C (77.2×10^{-2} cm³ CO₂ (STP)/(g·s) for the nanotube-shaped CeO₂ and 0.16×10^{-2} cm³ CO₂ (STP)/(g·s) for the powder CeO₂).

Cerium oxides have been the focus of intense research within the field of catalysis.¹ Either as pure dioxide, CeO₂, or doped with some transition metals (specially Zr) or lanthanide elements (Tb, Pr, La), it has been studied intensively as a redox component, the oxygen buffer, in three-way catalysts currently used in exhaust-gas converters of gasoline-fueled vehicles.^{2–4} More recently, ceria-containing oxides have shown to be highly interesting materials in new processes related to the production of hydrogen for fuel cells^{5–7} or the abatement of organic pollutants from industrial wastewater.^{8–10} Likewise they are being applied as polishing materials in optics,¹¹ as component of oxygen sensors,¹² or as solid electrolyte in fuel cells.¹³ In any case, the oxygen-handling properties of ceria is a key parameter in most of these applications.

The preparation of CeO₂ nanowires and nanotubes has been suggested as a way of improving catalytic and redox behavior.¹⁴ Thus, sol–gel, precipitation aging, hydrothermal, and nanoparticle self-assembling routes have been reported as ways to prepare nanowires and nanotubes made of cerium-containing compounds.^{14–22} In all cases, these are complex methods, involving a multistep synthesis process in which

some of the important steps usually involve a fine control of temperature and, also very often, of pressure.

Alumina membranes have been used as templates for the synthesis of nanowires and nanotubes of different materials.^{22–28} This methodology has rarely been used in the preparation of nanostructured cerium oxide.²² The method proposed in ref 22 is based on the electrolytic oxidation of a nonaqueous solution of CeCl₃. Nevertheless, concerning the preparation of ceria-based catalytic materials, the use of chloride-containing compounds must be avoided, since chlorides induce a significant deterioration of their redox capabilities,²⁹ on which most of their practical applications in catalysis are based. Due to this powerful poisoning effect, the use of chloride-free precursors is a necessary requisite in this case.

We have adapted and optimized the approach described in ref 23, proposed to prepare La(OH)₃ nanowires. This method is based on increasing pH inside the pores of the AAO template, which is obtained by the electrochemical reduction of nitrate ions of the La(NO₃)₃ employed as precursor. Finally, the pH increase allows La(OH)₃ to precipitate inside the AAO pores.

In this paper, commercial membranes of anodic alumina, 60 μm thick and with pore diameters of approximately 200

Figure 1. SEM images of fresh nanotubes after being extracted from the alumina template: (a) medium magnification and (b) high resolution.

nm, were employed. In order to perform the electrodeposition, a thin layer of gold was deposited on one face of the membranes. This treatment allows the membrane to be utilized as the cathode of a cell of three electrodes used in the process of electrodeposition. The electrical contact with the membrane is made by a copper plate on which the metalized face of the membrane is seated. The surface area of sample exposed to the solution is 1 cm². A net of platinum wires is employed as the auxiliary electrode, and one of Ag/AgCl (3 M) is employed as the reference electrode. The electrodeposition was performed during 1 h in a solution of 0.05 M Ce(NO₃)₃ at room temperature in the galvanostatic regime, applying 1 mA cm⁻².

When this solution is cathodically polarized, the reduction of the nitrate ions occurs in accordance with reaction in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Reduction Reaction of Nitrate Ions in the Cathode

This reaction provokes a local increase of the pH inside the nanopores and provides the conditions required for the precipitation of Ce(OH)₃, following the reaction in Scheme 2. However, it is well established that after exposure to air, even at room temperature, Ce(OH)₃ disproportionates into CeO₂ and H₂,³¹ Scheme 3. The occurrence of this reaction allows CeO₂ to be obtained, without any further treatment, avoiding the problems related to Ce(OH)₃ formation suggested in ref 22.

Scheme 2. Precipitation Reaction of Cerium Hydroxide as a Consequence of pH Increase

Scheme 3. Disproportionation Reaction of Ce(OH)₃

By using this direct, one-step process, ceria nanotubes with tunable length and diameters can be prepared by small, controlled, changes in the synthesis parameters. The procedure proposed here requires relatively short preparation times,

about 1 h, aqueous solutions, and only ambient temperatures and pressures, features which can be considered an advantage with respect to previously described methods.^{14–22} The most important thing is that, as it will be described later, the obtained nanotubes show improved catalytic properties with reference to those exhibited by powdered oxides.

Figure 1a includes a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the material obtained after an electrodeposition experiment followed by an immersion treatment of 3 h in 1.0 M NaOH solution. It can be observed in this image that this treatment enables the alumina membrane to dissolve and to separate it from the material formed inside the pores. As seen in Figure 1a, this procedure allows us to obtain cylindrical nanowires with diameters of 200 nm and a length of 30–40 μm. This diameter fits with those of the template pores. This result agrees with the mechanism proposed in the literature,²³ according to which, the nanowires are formed by precipitation of a lanthanide phase inside the pores. Nevertheless, high-magnification SEM images, such as the one displayed in Figure 1b, reveal that this procedure leads to the growth of nanotubes instead of nanowires.

In order to complete the characterization of the samples, structural studies were carried out by means of electron microscopy. High-resolution electron microscopy (HREM), high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) tomography, and analytical measurements by electron energy loss spectroscopy working in STEM mode (STEM-EELS) have been performed. Fresh as well as calcined (in an atmosphere of 5% O₂/He at 250 °C) nanotubes were studied. In Figure 2, HREM images corresponding to fresh nanotubes are included. The image shown in Figure 2a was acquired from the outer surface of a nanotube. In the right side of this image a dark band, corresponding to the wall of the tube, can be observed. By measurement of the width of this band, the wall thickness of the nanotubes was estimated to be on the order of 6 nm. These results suggest that the materials prepared are tubular structures. Figure 2a contains the digital diffraction pattern (DDP) generated calculating the fast Fourier transform of the HREM image included in the same figure. This DDP clearly shows the nanocrystalline nature of the analyzed nanotube. Thus, a ring of maximum intensity corresponding

Figure 2. HREM images of a fresh nanotube and corresponding DDPs of the (a) outer surface and (b) inner region.

Figure 3. Axial projection of a specimen tomogram in the xy direction (a), with successive slices through the xz direction (b–d) and the yz direction (e) indicated with arrows in (a).

to a lattice spacing of 0.31 nm is clearly identified, which is characteristic of the $\{111\}$ plane of the CeO_2 .³¹ In Figure 2b, a HREM image and its corresponding DDP acquired from inner areas of the fresh nanotubes are shown. As in the outer surface of the samples, this HREM image shows the presence of nanocrystalline domains of cerium dioxide. In these areas, although rings in the DDP still appear, the presence of reflections at well-defined positions is clear, indicating the existence of nanocrystals with preferential orientations. This “texture” is also apparent in the HREM image in Figure 2a.

HAADF-STEM tomography³² was performed in order to characterize the three-dimensional morphology of the nanotubes. The data for electron tomography were collected by tilting the specimen about a single axis with respect to the electron beam. A series of Z-contrast images of the sample was acquired every 2° between -76° and $+76^\circ$. Figure 3 shows the axial projection of a nanotube tomogram (Figure 3a) together with a series of single slices through the

tomogram. Panels b–d of Figure 3 show axial slices, from planes perpendicular to the tube axis, at different heights (marked in Figure 3a), and Figure 3e corresponds to a longitudinal slice on a plane containing the tube axis.

From this set of images it can be clearly seen that the nanotubes are actually hollow structures. Although the external walls grow to some extent toward the inside as corrugated lamellae, giving rise to a compartmentalized structure, a detailed analysis of the section of the tubes along their whole length reveals that the inner volume is connected along the tube axis, there being no fully closed compartments. Moreover, the presence of an inner-wall system provides some extra corrugation of the surface which results in a higher exposed area, a property of high relevance in applications related to catalysis. The dynamic three-dimensional visualization of the nanotube structure included as a video in the Supporting Information demonstrates this feature more clearly.

Figure 4. (a) STEM-HAADF image of a fresh nanotube. (b) EELS spectra taken at zones marked in (a). (c) Reference spectra for Ce(IV) and Ce(III) from ref 34.

The cerium oxidation state in the fresh and calcined samples was studied by combining STEM-HAADF images with EELS using a 0.5 nm probe size and a 10 cm camera length. The spectra were recorded in spot mode with 0.5 eV energy dispersion, using an acquisition time of 3–5 s and convergence and collection semiangles of 8 and 24 mrad, respectively. The background removal was performed using a window width of 50 eV of the Ce M_{4,5} edge and fitting to a power-law model.

The results obtained in the study of the fresh sample by means of STEM-EELS are included in Figure 4. Figure 4a displays a STEM-HAADF image of a fresh nanotube, and Figure 4b shows the EELS spectra recorded at the sites marked in the image. According to ref 33 the analysis of the fine structure of the M₄, M₅ lines of cerium makes it possible to discriminate between the Ce(III) and Ce(IV) species. The change in the oxidation state of cerium gives rise to three major effects: a significant change in the M₄/M₅ intensity ratio, a slight shift of the energy of these lines, and, finally, the appearance of small shoulders at higher energy loss in both lines. The comparison of reference spectra,³⁴ displayed in Figure 4c, with those recorded on the fresh nanotubes, Figure 4b, suggest that a mixture of Ce(III) and Ce(IV) is present in the as-prepared samples. The coexistence of both oxidation states can be more clearly appreciated in the spectrum acquired on the surface of the nanotube, position marked as 2 in the HAADF image of Figure 4a. The presence of both oxidation states indicates that, in addition to CeO₂, the fresh samples must contain nonstoichiometric ceria or a second, Ce(III)-rich phase, very likely Ce(OH)₃. The nanocrystalline nature of the tubes makes it difficult to identify in the HREM images individual crystals of any of these two phases. A comparison of the spectra obtained in the outer surface and in the inner areas of the nanotube walls suggests that the amount of Ce(III) is higher in the latter (compare spectra from areas 1 and 3 with those recorded on 2). This would indicate that the external surfaces of the nanotubes are enriched in CeO₂ in comparison

with the internal areas. These results can be interpreted bearing in mind that the synthesis method we have used should lead, initially, to the precipitation of Ce(OH)₃. However, as commented on above, the exposure of Ce(OH)₃ to air, even at room temperature, causes its disproportionation into CeO₂ and H₂.³⁰ The occurrence of such reaction at the external surface of the nanotubes would explain the Ce(IV) signal detected by EELS at this location. These results indicate that fresh nanotubes are heterogeneous with respect to the spatial distribution of the cerium oxidation state. However, if the Ce(OH)₃ nanotubes are kept in air, for a short period, at room temperature they will be fully transformed into fluorite-type CeO₂ nanotubes.

Catalytic activity tests usually involve initial surface cleaning routines, very often in the form of mild calcination pretreatments. In order to evaluate the effect of this kind of pretreatment on the nanostructure of the CeO₂ nanotubes, additional characterization studies have been performed after an oxidation in flowing 5% O₂/He mixture at 250 °C. Figure 5 includes HREM images and DDPs corresponding to the calcined nanotubes. It can be observed that after this treatment the tubular shape is retained. Figure 5a was recorded on the outer surface of the nanotubes, whereas Figure 5b corresponds to an inner area. Note how in this case there are no appreciable differences between the structures of these two locations. It is also worth noting the improvement in crystallinity after calcination. Nanotubes are made of an entangled conglomerate of more or less well faceted, nanocrystals, with sizes ranging from 1 to 3 nm, joined to each other in a complex fashion. The DDP included in Figure 5b shows a high number of discrete Bragg spots which can all be assigned to CeO₂. Figure 6 shows a HAADF image and three EELS spectra acquired on the nanotubes after calcination. EELS spectra were recorded on areas marked in the HAADF image. When these spectra are compared with those in Figure 4c, it appears that, in all analyzed areas, cerium is present in the structure as Ce(IV). This would confirm that the calcination treatment fully

Figure 5. (a) HREM images of a calcined nanotube and corresponding DDPs of the (a) outer surface and (b) inner zone.

Figure 6. (a) HAADF image of a calcined nanotube and (b) EELS analysis on different marked areas.

oxidizes the sample.

CeO₂ finds an application as a component in a variety of catalytic systems. In particular, its use as support of metallic catalysts employed for the oxidation of CO has drawn a large amount of interest.^{35–38} The kinetic mechanisms reported for this reaction consider that both the metallic phase and the support play a role in the activation of the CO oxidation. If so, the detailed features of the support structure would be expected to influence the catalytic behavior of these metal/CeO₂ systems. Therefore, it should be feasible that CeO₂ nanotubes such as those prepared here could show an improved behavior in this catalytic application. With this relationship in mind, measurements of the catalytic activity of calcined CeO₂ nanotubes within the AAO membrane in

Figure 7. Light-off curve corresponding to CeO₂-NT/AAO and powder CeO₂. Experimental conditions: amount of ceria sample, 10 mg total; flow rate, 100 cm³ min⁻¹; reaction mixture, 1% CO + 20% O₂ + He balance. Powder CeO₂ was diluted with crushed quartz.

the CO oxidation reaction were carried out. The results obtained in these experiments are presented in Figure 7 as a light-off curve. In these curves, the conversion of CO is represented as a function of the reaction temperature. These curves provide qualitative information about the catalytic behavior of the studied material. The so-called light-off temperature (LOT), which is the temperature at which 50% of conversion is reached, is usually employed as an activity evaluation parameter. In brief, the lower the value of this LOT, the better the catalytic activity of the tested material. Figure 7 includes the light-off curve of a powder CeO₂ sample, used as a reference, with 42 m² g⁻¹ of BET surface area, a value in the same order of magnitude as that corresponding to the CeO₂-NT/AAO system tested in this work, 20 m² g⁻¹. As can be observed, the LOT observed with the CeO₂-NT/AAO prepared here is 189 °C, while in the case of the conventional powder oxide this temperature is 300 °C. Powder CeO₂ shows negligible activity at temperatures below 200 °C, whereas the nanotube sample prepared here reaches a conversion close to 60% at this temperature. These results confirm that the CeO₂ nanotubes show a much improved catalytic performance. A comparison of the reaction rates observed with the two materials at the same temperature allows a more accurate quantification of the differences in the catalytic performance of the two materials. The catalytic activity values observed at moderate temperature, i.e., 200 °C, are the following (per gram of oxide): 77.2×10^{-2} cm³ CO₂ (STP)/(g·s) for the CeO₂-NT/AAO and 0.16×10^{-2} cm³ CO₂ (STP)/(g·s) for the powder CeO₂ oxide. These values indicate that the redox activity of the exposed CeO₂ surface of the nanotubes is much higher, more than 400 times that of a standard material. Other authors have obtained CeO₂ nanotubes with improved catalytic behavior in the oxidation of CO.¹⁴ Nevertheless, the enhancement observed is far from that reported by us. Thus, on the nanotubes prepared in ref 14, percent CO conversion starts to increase from 200 °C and a 3-fold increase of CO conversion, in comparison to bulk-CeO₂, is achieved at 250

°C. In contrast, our data show that at 200 °C the conversion already reaches a 60% value and a 400-fold increase in catalytic activity, with respect to conventional ceria powders, is observed at this temperature.

Although the origin of such a large difference in the catalytic performance needs a more detailed analysis, the in-depth characterization work carried out in the present paper, in parallel with available literature data, gives some keys to rationalize the effect in the first instance. Thus, according to our HREM characterization, the tubes are built by assembling a huge number of 1–3 nm size nanocrystals, randomly oriented to each other (Figure 5). This kind of nanostructuring provides the following: (1) small oxide crystal sizes, which can influence its intrinsic redox (oxygen-exchange) properties; (2) nanocrystallite morphologies which may involve the exposure at their surface of more reactive planes (probably {100} Type). Since different catalytic activity has been already found in CeO₂ materials as a function of the crystallographic nature of the exposed facets,³⁹ this may be a crucial factor; (3) the presence of a significant volume of boundary regions between the nanocrystals, at which the structure may be significantly distorted, and therefore being more reactive from both redox and catalytic points of view.

In summary, CeO₂ nanotubes have been grown electrochemically using a porous alumina membrane as template in only 1 h at room conditions. The morphological characterization states that the obtained nanotubes have diameters of 200 nm, which fits with those of the template pores, and lengths of 30–40 μm. Furthermore, the external walls grow in some zones toward the inside, generating connected and no fully closed compartments. The chemical characterization indicates the existence of Ce(III) and Ce(IV) in the freshly prepared material. Finally, the oxidation treatment applied here leads to the homogenization of the composition, giving rise to nanotubes of CeO₂, without changes of morphology. These CeO₂ nanotubes show a catalytic activity in CO oxidation, at 200 °C, around 400 times higher than powdered CeO₂. This highly improved catalytic performance must be due to the fact that the nanotubes are built by assembling a huge number of 1–3 nm size nanocrystals, randomly oriented to each other, giving rise to a significant volume of very reactive boundary regions between the nanocrystals. Likewise, a greater contribution of the more reactive {100} facets to the surface structure of the material may also contribute to the observed catalytic performance enhancement.

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Supporting Information Available: A movie of the full dynamic tomogram is included, showing a 3D view of the cerium nanotube together with the slices through the reconstructed nanotube. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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